

EFFECT OF POLYPHENOLS ISOLATED FROM EUPHORBIA FRANCHETII (B.FEDTSCH) ON LPO PROCESSES IN MITOCHONDRIA

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The production of free radicals in various tissues and cells of the body through many endogenous and exogenous pathways causes oxidative stress, which leads to the development of various diseases in humans. Therefore, the study of the antioxidant properties of biologically active substances isolated from plants is of great importance. It is known that epidemiologically, fruits and vegetables rich in antioxidants in the diet prevent the development of many diseases associated with oxidative stress. Recent studies have shown that mitochondria play an important role in apoptotic and necrotic cell death. As a result of mitochondrial dysfunction, the number of mitochondria in tissues decreases, deep ultrastructural anomalies of organelles develop, mitochondrial biogenesis is disrupted, the activity of enzyme complexes of the respiratory chain changes, and ATP synthesis is inhibited. At the same time, mitochondrial dysfunction can lead to calcium homeostasis disruption, excessive production of reactive oxygen species, as well as the transition of the megapore to an open conformation, a decrease in the expression of the antiapoptotic protein Bcl-2, the release of cytochrome c, the activation of proapoptotic caspase-3 and the DNA repair enzyme poly (-ADP-ribose) polymerase. From the above, it can be seen that a specific mitochondrial dysfunction is observed in the process of lipid peroxidation (LPO) that develops during oxidative stress.

Purpose of the study. Therefore, the study investigated the effect of 1-O-galloyl-4,6-hexahydroxydiphenoyl- β -D-glucose polyphenol isolated from *the Euphorbia franchetii* plant on the LPO process in rat liver mitochondria.

Materials and methods of the study. Rat liver mitochondria were isolated by differential centrifugation. The composition of the separation medium: 250 mM sucrose, 10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH-7.4. IM : KCl - 125 mM, Tris-HCl - 10 mM, pH 7.4; The process of lipid peroxidation (LPO) in mitochondria was induced in the presence of 10 μ M FeSO₄, 600 μ M ascorbic acid. The protein content in the cuvette was 0.3-0.4 mg/ml. The mitochondrial fluorescence was determined at 540 nm using a V-5000 spectrophotometer.

Results and their analysis. The change in the intensity of the LPO process in mitochondria under the influence of Fe²⁺ /ascorbate was set as 100% control. 1-O-galloyl-4,6-hexahydroxydiphenoyl- β -D-glucose to the incubation medium when polyphenol substance is added in the amount of 1 μ M, the LPO process is increased by 21 \pm 1.7%, in the amount of 2 μ M by 39 \pm 1.31%, in the amount of 3 μ M by 54 \pm 2.2%, in the amount of 4 μ M by 74 \pm 1.91%, in the amount of 5 μ M It was found that it inhibited by 88 \pm 1.7%.

Conclusion. The results show that 1-O-galloyl-4,6-hexahydroxydiphenoyl- β -D-glucose polyphenol exhibited high antioxidant activity at the low micromolar concentrations studied. It

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inhibited the Fe²⁺/ascorbate-induced LPO process in mitochondria and exhibited membrane-active properties.